

Consumer Electronics

Mr. A. Tharik Basha, MBA

Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce

AVS College of Arts and Science, Salem

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month:

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-4168

E-ISSN: 2582-0729

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Tharik Basha,
A. "Consumer
Electronics." *Shanlax
International Journal of
Commerce*, vol. 7,
no. S1, 2019,
pp. 235–36.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.3451708](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3451708)

Introduction to Modern Marketing

Marketing refers to activities undertaken by a business to promote the buying or sale of a product or service. Marketing includes selling, advertising, and delivering products to consumers or other businesses.

Marketing as a discipline involves all the actions a company undertakes to draw in consumers and keep relations with them. Networking with potential or past clients is part of the job too, including writing thank you emails, playing golf with a prospective client, responding emails and calls immediately, and meeting with clients for a meal or a coffee.

At its most basic, selling seeks to match a company's services and products to consumers who want access to those products. The matching of product to customer ultimately ensures profitability.

Digital Marketing ERA

Digital marketing is the use of the internet, mobile devices, search engines, social media, and other channels to reach consumers. Some marketing experts consider digital marketing to be an entirely new endeavor that requires a new way of approaching customers and new ways of learning how customers behave correlated to traditional marketing.

Digital marketing targets a specific section of the customer base and is interactive. Digital shopping is on the rise and includes email ads, search result ads, and improved tweets – anything that incorporates marketing with consumer feedback or a two-way interaction between the corporation and customer.

Consumer Electronics

The consumer assets sector is a category of stocks and companies that relate to items purchased by individuals rather than by entrepreneurs and industries. This sector includes companies involved with packaged goods, food production, clothing, beverages, electronics, and automobiles.

Organizations doing market in the consumer goods industry in 2018 are currently developing newer and more daring strategies to execute traditional levers against a backdrop of a more stable US and worldwide economy. Among the current trends are emergent trends and markets, innovation, M & M activity, and digitization.

Products In Consumer Electronics

- Television
- Refrigerator
- Air Conditioner
- Mobiles
- Personal Computer (PC) / Laptops
- Electronics – Gadgets

Buying & Selling Aspects

Buying

Buying is an important function. Business concerns and consumers spend more time in buying goods. Buying includes the determining of one’s need, finding out the source of supply, the making of business connections, the negotiating of prices and other terms and conditions and the transfer of title from the seller to the purchaser.

Selling

Selling is the other side of the exchange function. Selling is the heart of the marketing task. Selling in business means the transfer of ownership of goods or services to a buyer in exchange for money. Selling function is also a creative function. It creates demand. Without selling, there is no buying. The main object of selling is to sell or to dispose of goods at a satisfactory price.

Price Strategy

Pricing assumes a significant role in a competitive economy. Price is the main factor which affects the sales organization. The good price policy is of great importance to the producers, wholesalers, retailers & customers.

If the prices are high few buyers purchases & if the prices are low, many buyers purchases. That is the prices increases in relations to the sales revenue.

Thus, pricing is a critical situation. Therefore, a sound pricing policy must be adopted to have a maximum sales revenue.

Advertising

An advertisement has a prominent place among the techniques of mass education and persuasion on the public. It is not a modern origin. It has been used from the immemorial period. In early periods, the advertisement was displayed in the form of signboards, writing on the historical buildings, etc.. now manufactures, business man, employers, new shop owners, marketers, etc.. are benefited greatly by displaying advertising. Its purpose is to inform or influence them to increase the sale of the advertiser.

E-business

E-business describes the use of electronic means and platform to conduct a company’s business. The appearance of the internet has greatly increased the ability of businesses to conduct their business faster, more accurately at reduced cost and with the ability to customize and personalize customer offerings. Internet or E-auctioning, E-banking, E-mailing, E-learning, E-marketing, E-trading, etc.

Conclusion

The development of marketing is evolutionary rather than revolutionary. The marketing has been defined differently by authorities in different ways. The traditional objective of marketing has been to make the goods at places where they needed. In the 2010s, most of the consumer electronics have become based on consumerization of information technology. The CEA(consumer electronic association) estimated the value of 2015 consumer electronic sales at the US \$ 220 billion.